

Results from the joint IRENA and IEECP workshop: Stakeholder-driven scenarios for a just transition to climate neutrality, 18.11.2023

How can we become better in engaging stakeholders in scenario and modelling processes? Think of different requirements, methods, tools etc.

- Set clear objectives and goals for the modelling
- Honest engagement, no “engagement-washing”
- Map relevant stakeholders and be open when identifying stakeholders
- Engage stakeholders early, continuously in the modelling process, not only passively as respondents
- Be transparent about the consultation process: present a roadmap
- Have a trusted intermediary facilitating the process
- Understand the different priorities and potential agendas of different stakeholders
- Create “safe spaces” for stakeholder engagement
- Apply co-creative approaches to apply mutual understanding of different approaches, and to allow different perspectives to be considered
- Use innovative methods to facilitate the exchange between modellers and model-users; e.g. models could be used to visualise potential changes to communities, or opinion could be collected via social media apps.
- Use AI and digitalisation for engagement
- Create a community of practice

- background education on energy systems

- watch out for "engagement washing"

How can we become better in engaging stakeholders in scenario & modelling processes?

- Comprehensive mapping and seeking complementarity
- Openness ^{and} when identifying stakeholders
- Clear communication (limitations, scope, ...)
- Understanding the priorities and agendas of the stakeholders
- The description of the scenarios ⁺
- Safe Spaces ⁺ → Starting from injustices, not just aiming for perfectly just (what makes you angry?)
- Using AI and digitalization + VR
- Bring relevant KPIs to ensure understanding
- Trusted intermediary administering the process
- co-creation → also during problem formulation - not only at the end
- How are you engaging? (not only why) ~~same~~
(ant ex ante) - # of sessions, who, what channels, made
↳ **present a roadmap** for consultation process

What are the gaps of energy models to inform just energy transitions?

- Insufficient expectation management – what can the model tell us and what not?
- Lack to consider broader social and economic impacts, including impacts on employment
- Lack to consider distributional impacts of scenarios – winners and losers
- Lack of interdisciplinarity of teams; no sufficient social science
- Lack of model transparency
- No one-model-fits-all
- Underestimation of growth potentials of renewables
- Old energy biases, e.g. base load
- Lack of awareness and treatment of model uncertainties
- Lack of available data, e.g. to perform costs-benefit analysis
- Actions of smaller households and communities are not reflected
- Deficit in representing complexities of new energy systems
- Missing link between inputs and outputs of different modelling tools; lack of model comparisons
- Lack of consideration of who uses the models and interprets the results

What are the gaps of energy modelling to inform just energy transition

• Meaningful Interdisciplinary Socio-Economic Modelling.

- irreducibility of justice → need for complementary methods

- No one-size-fits-all approach
- Under Estimation of RE Technologies' exponential growth rate.
- Avoid old energy biases (baseload, ...)
- Sensitivity to the particular definitions of JET
- Encourage research in social science and build interdisciplinary modelling
- Lack of available data to measure cost benefit analysis of policies
 - accounting for individual impacts of a system (e.g. storage policies)
- Transparency
 - dependent upon sufficient data
- Awareness and treatment of uncertainties
 - ↳ aleatory technical U.
 - ↳ epistemic (human, business)
 - ↳ data might not exist
 - ↳ ground verification + comparisons (e.g. speed of implementation)
- expectation management
 - ↳ what is the model telling us?
 - ↳ greater detail of metrics
 - ↳ being transparent about limitations
- topic of model, access to model
 - ↳ e.g. electricity access, urban models w/ detail
 - ↳ e.g. open source.

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How can we make models & modelling processes more inclusive and fair?

- Transparency of the modelling process, including clarity of the data and assumptions used and the outputs
- Increasing and continuous engagement of different stakeholders including civil society to ensure that different perspectives are represented in the models
- Create “safe spaces” for an open discussion; can be online or offline workshops, one-on-one debates
- Be clear about the mental model of the person who is building the model – independent team would be ideal
- Leverage existing consultation processes
- Capacity building of stakeholders about energy modelling
- Consideration of questions of fairness and affordability in modelled policy options; inclusion of representation of decentralised actors in the design of different scenarios
- Work with case studies to assess impacts of the transformation, including costs and benefits
- Setting up of a diverse advisory board
- More social scientific research to better understand social aspects, such as lived energy experiences or energy poverty; expand the sensitivity of the model to social aspects
- Recognition of the importance of stakeholder engagement in funding
- Create a user-experience around the model

How can we make models & modeling processes more inclusive & fair (think about processes & outcomes)?

- leverage existing consultation processes (regulatory) ~~(regulatory)~~
- co-creation at the research design stage

→ Promote openness and create safe spaces
Who is building the model → independent team = ideal
What funding mechanisms exist? → or... publicly-funded support? (jury duty)
Or by private company supported.

Reporting requirements: e.g. assumptions, outputs, sensitivity analysis

Environment for participation, e.g. in person, in one-on-ones, site/location

SENSELESS LIMITS/CONSTRAINTS ON PRIVATE COMPANY/LOBBY PART!
mode (virtual vs. in-person), ~~time~~
Speaker selection & order, time of day

Inclusion of Decentralised Actors. Community Power

Calibrated stakeholder engagement

Creating a user experience around the model and the outcomes

Expand the sensitivity of the models to social options science decision alternatives

How should energy scenarios and models be improved to better contribute to policy debates?

- Early engagement to ensure policy relevance of results; framing of the work within existing policy questions
- Develop models that are complex enough but not too complex
- Be clear about the intended modelling outcomes
- Communicate about underlying norms and values
- Communicate relevance of the work and social and economic impacts
- Provide information on possible technologies and regional solutions
- Be transparent with assumptions and data (open science)
- Include more exploratory scenarios
- Perform a risk assessment
- Leverage social science in understanding people's attitudes
- Develop inactive dashboards or displays to engage with the model
- Let stakeholder engage with different indicators and let them weight them
- Enable a policy dialogue
- Prepare communication materials with clear representation of results
- Maintain models well

How should energy scenarios and energy ~~scenarios~~ models be improved to better contribute to policy debates?

- Clearer description of intended modelling outputs, e.g. via better scenario names, motivation statement (existing policies & laws)
- engaging with policymakers, framing within existing policy questions
- flexible & adaptable models to changing political priorities, events, regulations
↳ e.g. geographic scope, technologies, scenarios
- Risk analysis as part of modelling study & reporting requirements
- communication incl. visualization, media (report + video + ...)
- leverage social sciences in understanding people's attitudes → bring more meaning to modelling process
- probabilistic success rates on project completion → e.g. scenarios where project can't be completed due to activist action

Clear solutions for the problems of the world

More effective Outreach of Outcomes

Look at all possible ^{CLEAN} technologies and regional

Incorporate more exploratory ^{Solutions} scenarios

Communicate about underlying norms and values.

Some other notes:

- What is the target of the modelling? How do we define the target with stakeholders? Do we talk about 100% renewables?
- Short-term versus long-term scenarios
- Challenge of cultural clashes
- Historical modelling tools, institutional side of modelling
- Role of people in the energy system is changing – needs to be reflect in modelling
- Modellers also must learn what policymaking is about
- Modellers must become good listeners
- How can we connect global, European, national modelling to the local level?
- Stakeholder engagement can enable to get ideas of future energy systems
- Complexity of models versus simple to understand models
- Jobs in the transition – how can account for employment impacts?